

A comparative analysis of UK sustainable housing standards

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Abstract

Over the last few decades, the UK government has developed several sustainability policies, namely the National Planning Policy Framework, the Building Regulations Part-L, the Environmental Impact Assessment and others form the basis for sustainable housing provision in the UK. However, studies by the UK Green Building Council have shown that developers are not familiar with or do not adopt all parts of these regulations and standards, citing complexity and rising costs as barriers. We suggest that the complexity, fragmentation and misunderstanding of sustainability regulations and standards must be overcome in order to effectively design sustainable housing. This study argues that a mapping of existing sustainability standards and their use would help in this endeavour. This will be done firstly to identify sustainable housing standards and discuss their structure and challenges, and secondly to examine their effectiveness in delivering sustainable housing by conducting a comparative analysis that identifies similarities, differences and relationships between regulations and standards. A literature review was used to identify relevant UK sustainability regulations. This served as the basis for a comparative analysis examining the scope, applicability, areas of intervention and methods of sustainability regulations and standards. In addition, a desktop analysis was conducted on three case studies of sustainable housing in England to identify the building standards applied and assess their effectiveness in terms of the project's environmental impacts and sustainability outcomes. The result of this study contributes to the theoretical discourse on sustainability regulations and standards. It presents a comprehensive mapping the existing regulatory structure of sustainability in housing with its challenges to help developers navigate the complexities.

Keywords: UK Sustainable housing, sustainability standards, regulatory structure.

1. Introduction

In the pursuit of mitigating climate change and reducing emissions, the United Kingdom's government has committed to improving the energy efficiency of the housing sector to a minimum of EPC-C rating by 2030 (NHF, 2021), and simultaneously to reducing the country greenhouse gas emissions by at least 100 per cent of 1990 levels by 2050 (CCC, 2019). The National Planning Policy Framework emphasised the role of sustainability standards and regulations in enforcing and supporting such a commitment (MHCLG, 2021). However, pursuing this commitment is faced with a long history of reluctance by some developers to fully

embrace sustainability within the housing sector (UKGBC, 2021). Tracing the roots of this reluctance, was primarily explained through the UK regulatory structure and its failure to produce simple and effective regulations and standards. Pickvance (2009) explained that the complexity of the regulations has reached a level that cannot be fully understood, and enforcement has become burdensome on local governments (Pickvance, 2009). Echoing these concerns, the Environmental Audit Committee's 2013 report concluded that sustainability regulations make the house-building process unnecessarily expensive and complicated (EAC, 2013a), and require a complete review and restructuring to simplify the "*untenable forest of codes*" (EAC, 2013b, p. 11). The Building a Safer Future report, commonly referred to as "The 2018 Hackitt Review of Building Regulations", added that existing building regulations, including those governing sustainability compliance, suffer from inadequacies, inconsistencies and lack of clarity (Hackitt, 2018).

This study, therefore, discusses the current regulatory structure governing sustainability in UK housing sector with a particular focus on energy efficiency and carbon dioxide emissions. with the aim of mapping the current landscape of sustainability regulations and standards followed in housing provision. It also aims to identify and compare the similarities, differences and relationships between the various regulatory tools. This is an essential step in assessing the effectiveness of regulations in achieving the UK's vision of a decarbonised housing sector by 2050.

Two strands of methods were used. First, a literature review was undertaken to understand the structure of sustainability regulations and to map the different types of regulations and standards. Second, a desktop analysis of three case studies in England was conducted to examine the typology of the project, the sustainability regulations applied and the outcome of the development in terms of energy efficiency, carbon emission and the regulatory structure adopted.

The findings of this study clarify the current regulatory structure and identify three overlapping levels of regulation – national, regulators and local – that play a crucial role in producing and regulating housing sustainability. In addition, a mapping of regulations and standards was created, identifying two types of sustainability regulations – mandatory and voluntary – and shedding light on their role and effectiveness. Both the explanation and the mapping contribute to the sustainability discourse in housing from a theoretical perspective, help housing developers understand the complexity of the typology and structure of sustainability regulations, and highlight the regulatory challenges facing the housing sector.

2. Context

To comprehend the UK sustainability regulation, it is important to first examine the structure of the UK regulatory system and then review the sustainability standards for housing and their development as outlined in the following sections.

2.1 The structure of the UK regulatory system

Unlike many other countries, the UK regulatory framework is designed to operate at different parallel levels — local authority, national regulators and central government departments — which complement each other to provide a range of mechanisms and to ensure sufficient integration and monitoring of national development objectives (BRDO, 2009).

At the local government level, planning is structured as a two-tier system consisting of county councils and district councils depending on the area size. This dual structure aims to support local authorities in the formulation and implementation of responsive planning policies (BRDO, 2009). Local authorities have a range of responsibilities including developing city-town-parish and community plans, addressing housing and sustainability issues, and promoting community engagement (Cornwall, 2021). They also enforce the statutory regulations and standards set out in the Regulatory Enforcement and Sanctions Act 2008 (BRDO, 2009).

At the national regulatory level, an intermediary structure works with the Primary Authority — a supporting legislative system — these entities collaborate to enhance the consistency of local regulations, align local authority plans with the national framework, and promote cooperation between local authorities to ensure consistent and equitable application of the law (OPS&S, 2017). In the context of housing and sustainability in England, various regulatory bodies exist, such as the Environment Agency, the Regulator of Social Housing, the Building Safety Inspectorate and the National Construction Products Regulator (DLUHC, 2022).

At the national level, national regulatory frameworks are governed by central departments. Two overlapping mechanisms define their operation. The first mechanism includes broad strategies such as the Sustainable Development Indicators (SDIs), which articulate the government's vision and goals for addressing sustainability challenges. The second, narrower mechanism prescribes technical requirements that specify construction techniques and processes to achieve the objectives of the national strategy. An example of this are the building regulations (DEFRA, 2013; Oyebanji, 2014).

It could be noted that the current sustainability standards, codes and regulations for housing have become the core of the UK planning system. The following section therefore focuses on the current sustainability standards and codes for housing.

2.2 The UK housing sustainability policy classification and review

The concept of sustainable housing policy dates back to the early 1990s, which emerged to address climate change issues (Sunikka & Boon, 2003). However, it was not until 2005 that the first binding code — The Code for Sustainable Homes (CSH) — was developed. This was shortly followed by the government's Zero Carbon for New Homes by 2016 strategy in 2006, and later the 2007 Housing Green Paper, all of which set the foundation for sustainability policies, codes and standards in UK housing. By looking at the work of Oyebanji (2014), Hannigan (2006), Carter et al. (2007), DCLG (2004–14), DLHC (2019–22) and others. A four-sided categorisation of policy emerges. The first quadrant focuses on curbing energy consumption and CO₂ emissions, exemplified by the Sustainable Energy Act. The second quadrant focuses on the function of rating systems to promote sustainability, e.g. energy performance certificates. The third quadrant covers technical aspects of construction, such as Part L of the Building Regulations. The fourth quadrant highlights the planning influence of local authorities, as exemplified by the National Planning Policy Framework. Regardless of the category, however, several connotations can be identified. First, the rapid policy changes have created confusion and uncertainty, exacerbating the challenge for the industry to adapt to new policies and leading to a purposeful disregard for the integration of sustainability by developers (UKGBC,

2017). Second, achieving sustainability goals proved elusive even with the singular policy approach (such as CSH) mainly due to the complicated nature of the code and its lack of integration with other policies, which imposed a significant administrative burden on the building sector (EAC, 2013b). Third, most policies focus on performance targets and specify desired outcomes without prescribing precise methods, leaving much room for misinterpretation and negligence (Rankl, 2023).

In housing sustainability, regulations can be categorised into two main types: compulsory and voluntary standards, each playing a distinct role within the overarching policy framework. At the national level, there are mandatory regulations, including the Building Regulations, Town and County Planning and the Energy Performance Certification Scheme (BRAC, 2010). These serve as the basic requirements for all developments, and often complemented by conditional policy such as the Environmental Impact Assessment scheme. Local authorities contribute to this landscape with their own policies, and compliance with these local policies is conditional. Like the national policies, building regulations use a performance-based, descriptive approach. For example, they require buildings to meet energy efficiency criteria but do not prescribe specific insulation or heating systems (Rankl, 2023).

Voluntary standards, in contrast, are not legally mandated but set higher sustainability targets and provide detailed codes and guidelines. The recent Policy Playbook published by the UK Green Buildings Council (2020) noted that among many the Home Quality Mark (HQM) and the Passivhaus standards are the most prominent, in which both are regarded as the baseline for sustainability to be used by developers and local councils. The HQM, developed by the Building Research Establishment (BRE), rates housing developments based on their performance in a number of areas, including energy efficiency, environmental impact, materials used, amenities, indoor air quality and overall quality of life for residents (BRE, 2018). The Passivhaus Standard, focuses on energy and heating and aims to reduce energy consumption and improve indoor comfort (Hines et al., 2015).

It is observable that sustainability standards and regulations differ significantly between mandatory and voluntary and that energy is central to both. The following section explains the methods in this study and the formulation of the results.

3. Methods

Comparative analysis is a well-established method in the social sciences that aims to examine and compare two or more entities, elements, variables or cases to identify similarities and differences. This study used two methods to collect the data needed for the analysis, as explained in Figure 1. The academic literature, such as peer-reviewed articles, provided the theoretical understanding needed to discuss the structure and challenges of the UK regulatory system. The grey literature, such as government reports and regulations, on the other hand, helped to create the intended sustainability mapping. Both have informed the case study analysis, which sets the variables for comparing the standards and regulations examined and their effectiveness, as explained in the following sections.

Figure 1. Methods mapping. Source: The authors, 2023.

3.1 Literature

The purpose of examining the literature was to establish an overarching understanding of the UK regulatory structure, sustainability regulations typologies and interrelationships between sustainability policies and their instruments. As well as identifying the criteria needed to conduct a comparative analysis of sustainability regulation adopted at various scales with a focus on housing. The process of literature selection is pivotal to qualitative studies. Therefore, at the outset of this study, inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined based on: (1) pertinence to the study's overarching discourse, (2) the authority and credibility of sources, and (3) material impact, gauged quantitatively through citation metrics (Mensah & Enu-Kwesi, 2018). Secondary data was collected by reviewing relevant materials, including peer-reviewed articles, books, conference proceedings and other documents available in specialised databases such as web of science. The identification of sources employed a combination of keyword searches related to topics such as UK regulatory structure, sustainable buildings standards, and mandatory building regulations. The search was limited to the period from 2000 onwards. However, attention was also paid to older sources if they significantly contributed to the ongoing discourse on the topics.

3.2 Case studies

Case study is a valuable approach for exploring a particular phenomenon and gaining insights in social sciences (Yin, 2014). The purpose of this method in this study is to validate the comparison of the codes derived from the literature review, as well as to compare the results of different sustainable housing projects in terms of regulations and standards typology and their effectiveness. However, the selection of cases was primarily influenced by Yin (2014) criteria, including (1) relevance to the problem under study, as all cases are sustainable housing projects that comply with mandatory regulations and adopt additional standards, (2) variation that allows for meaningful comparisons and identification of patterns or themes where different voluntary standards have been adopted, and (3) data availability from multiple sources. Data for the cases analysed included planning reports, sustainability statements, planning applications and sustainability reports, all obtained from the designers or the local council planning portal. Cases were selected from the Housing Design Award archive — a UK-based competition for sustainable housing projects — proving a wide range of projects recognised as best practices in sustainability and housing design. The selection process is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Case studies database screening process. Source: The authors, 2023.

Three projects were identified as suitable for this study with data available from multiple sources. These are Deben Fields in Felixstowe, Riverside Road, and Old Ford Road both in London. Figure 3 illustrates the cases and their locations. A desktop analysis, then was carried out to identify (1) the nature of the development as qualitatively described in the planning application and design statement submitted to the local authorities, (2) the sustainability policies, regulations, standards and codes applied as explained in the compliance reports, and (3) the outcome of the development analysed against the environmental impact score obtained from the EPC archive, measured by CO2 emission and energy rating.

Figure 3. Case studies plans and perspectives. Source: The authors adopted from TateHindle (2021), BPA (2020), and pH+ (2016).

Deben Fields Affordable and Sustainable Housing Project

The Deben Fields project, located near Felixstowe in Suffolk, England, comprises 61 affordable and sustainable family housing units. Designed by TateHindle Architects. It embodies a vision for an environmentally, socially, and economically sustainable project that prioritises people, their experiences, and nature. The project embraces a fabric-first approach and modern methods of construction to achieve higher sustainability goals (TateHindle, 2021). To attain sustainability goals, the project goes

beyond mandatory policies and regulations. It adheres to higher sustainability standards covering areas such as energy efficiency, water consumption, overheating, and material use. Four types of policies were adopted: (1) compulsory national standards, including paragraphs 117 to 127 of the National Planning Policy Framework and Building Regulations – Part L, (2) compulsory local policies, like the Suffolk Coastal Local Plan 2020, emphasising alternative strategies for sustainable outcomes, and (3) conditional and voluntary standards, like the Passivhaus standards and Regulation 18(3-4) of the EIA. The project has achieved a 20 per cent improvement in CO₂ reduction compared to building regulations requirements, calculated through SAP, and maintains water usage below 110 litres/person/day. It also integrates sustainability features such as passive solar gain and photovoltaic cells

Riverside Road Family Houses Project

The Riverside Road comprises five sustainable family housing units located in Watford, London, England. Developed for Watford Borough Council as a temporary housing scheme to address housing shortages, the project aligns with the council's vision for highly sustainable housing. It employs passive measures to minimise in-use energy demand and adopts the HQM assessment to exceed standard building control regulations (BPA, 2020). To realise the council's vision of highly sustainable housing, the project adopts various policies: (1) compulsory national standards, including the National Planning Policy Framework, and Building Regulations – Part L, (2) compulsory local policies, like Watford Borough Council's Core Strategy and policies on sustainable design and climate change, and (3) voluntary standards, including HQM standards and Regulation 18(3-4) of the EIA. Assessed through an EPC, the project achieved a 68 per cent improvement in CO₂ reduction and energy use compared to Part L. It also attained a four out of five-star rating in the HQM assessment.

Old Ford Road Housing Estate

The Old Ford Road housing estate, a privately owned project comprising eight housing units, is situated in the London Borough of Tower Hamlets, within the Victoria Park Conservation Area, London, England. Due to site conditions and negotiations with the local council, the project takes a unique approach to address sustainability policies without imposing excessive financial burdens on the owners (pH+, 2016). This project adhered only to mandatory sustainability policies and regulations, like the National Planning Policy Framework, Building Regulations – Part L, Tower Hamlets Core Strategy (2010), and Tower Hamlets Development Management (2013). Despite the project's reluctance to adopt higher sustainability standards, it achieved notable reductions in CO₂ emissions, attaining a class B-EPC score, and significantly reducing water and energy consumption, as measured by SAP assessment (pH+, 2016).

3.3 Analytical framework

It is essential to establish a comparative framework that specifies the comparison variables and clarifies the purpose and extent of the units being compared. Therefore, the comparison variables in this study were derived from the literature reviewed. They include (1) the scope of the regulation as qualitatively described in the NPPF, (2) applicability, which clarifies the legal status of the standards, (3) the intervention areas, which examine the targeted aspects of development, such as energy and water

consumption and emission rates, (4) the intervention methods, which examine the standards' approach as descriptive, quantitative or both, (5) effectiveness, which compares the projects outcome in terms of their CO2 and energy rating against the UK national vision of zero carbon country by 2050.

4. Findings and discussion

This section is structured to present the findings derived from the literature and the case studies, divided into the mapping and the discussion of the effectiveness.

4.1 Mapping sustainability regulations and standards

To carry out the intended comparison, Figure 4 was created to map the similar, unique and conflicting criteria of the investigated mandatory regulations (Figure 4 bottom side) and voluntary standards (Figure 4 upper side). To create the mapping, the compulsory regulations and voluntary standards identified from the literature and case studies were examined by breaking them down into their impact areas and then mapping the criteria that directly relate to sustainability. To explain, the HQM lists 39 criteria that need to be addressed. However, only 22 criteria that are considered directly related to sustainability are listed in Figure 4. For example, criterion 3.3 Security was not mapped as it relates to building security, crime and tenants. The mapped criteria were then compared on the basis of scope, applicability, focus and method, as explained in section 3.2 and complemented in the following subsections.

Figure 4. Mapping of UK sustainability regulations and standards. Source: The authors, 2023.

Scope: Part L focuses primarily on energy, emissions and fuel use; it also defines the building's energy performance requirements. The Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), on the other hand, is used to assess the potential environmental impact of the proposed project compared to a baseline condition. The standard assessment procedure (SAP) evaluates how much energy a dwelling will consume if

it provides a certain level of comfort and services. The assessment is based on standardised assumptions for occupancy and behaviour. In contrast, a Home Quality Mark (HQM) is a detailed review and design standards that target three main areas: home, delivery and management. In addition, Passivhaus is a clear standard that aims only to reduce a building's energy consumption for heating and cooling while maintaining high levels of indoor comfort and air quality. It is also worth noting that several Part L criteria conflict with both HQM and Passivhaus. For example, the Building Regulations set the average CO2 emissions of a household at 4.5 tonnes per year, whereas the HQM sets this at 0.9 tonnes per year.

Applicability and legal status: Part-L and the SAP are mandatory regulations, which means all new buildings must comply with the requirements set by their criteria. EIA on the other hand, is a conditional provision and is only applicable and mandatory if local councils consider that the development may have a particular impact on the environment. In the meantime, both HQM and Passivhaus are voluntary. However, in some cases it has been noted that local councils encourage their adaptation as they offer a higher sustainability target.

Intervention focus and area: The focus of Part L is on energy and emissions. Therefore, the intervention is primarily centred on calculating energy consumption and CO2 emissions. The EIA focuses on population, health and ecological context. SAP's emphasis is on the complex elements of construction and includes the building structure (walls, roofs, floors and windows) and the building systems such as heating and cooling. The Passivhaus, however, adds the aspects of the climate within the buildings as well as the behaviour of the users and the impact on electricity consumption. HQM is the most comprehensive standard, addressing transportation, indoor and outdoor climate, electricity, water, construction management and post-occupancy evaluation.

Intervention methods: The qualitative approach predominates in mandatory regulations, as the regulations do not specify construction methods but set a minimum standard to be achieved. In contrast, voluntary standards use quantitative and qualitative methods to describe the desired outcome, the best method to achieve that outcome and performance benchmarks.

4.2 Effectiveness of regulations and standards

To establish a baseline for comparing effectiveness. Two variables were examined as derived from the literature reviewed. First, the degree of regulatory complexity which is measured by the number of regulations and standards adopted. Figure 5 was developed to illustrate the numbers associated with each project.

Figure 5. Number of regulations adopted for each case study. Source: The authors, 2023.

The Deben Fields project had the highest number of regulations and standards adopted (51). However, sustainability regulations at the local level had the most significant impact, with 12 policies targeting different areas of sustainability in housing. Riverside Road, on the other hand, had 49 different standards applied. Most notable is the Adoption of the HQM, which sets out 22 aspects for sustainability measures. Old Ford Road has only followed the mandatory requirements, setting 16 different elements with the lowest level of regulatory complexity.

The second variable is assessing the project's environmental impact, which follows the same principle as BRE's benchmark assessment method. It compares the simulated development outcome in terms of carbon emissions and energy rating using the SAP method. Figure 6 shows each project's carbon emissions and energy rating (EPC).

Figure 6. Environmental impact of each case study. Source: The authors, 2023.

Figure 6 shows that the projects that used voluntary standards had better energy scores and lower CO2 emissions. Although the Old Ford Road project only complied with the mandatory standards, CO2 emissions were lower than the maximum allowed under the building regulations because, in addition to the building regulations, the project complied with the council's sustainability guidelines, which require strict reductions in CO2 emissions.

A triad of connotations is noted by coupling the findings of Figure 5 with Figure 6. First, following only the mandatory regulations enacted at the national and local levels has significantly improved results over the existing building stock. Compared to the average Class D rating in England, the Old Ford Road project has achieved a Class B energy rating, and carbon emissions have been reduced to 1.9 tonnes, an improvement of around 68 per cent on existing CO2 production levels. Secondly, a higher number of standards does not necessarily lead to a better outcome, as shown

by the example of Deben Fields adopting a more complex regulatory structure and 85 per cent improvement in CO₂ reduction, while Riverside Road has used a less complex structure and reduced the CO₂ emissions by 86.5 per cent of the national average. Thirdly, none of the projects achieved the UK vision of net zero by 2050.

To summarise, it can be deduced from these connotations that the Part-L building regulations, in combination with local authority regulations, are the least effective compared to projects that have adopted voluntary standards. Adopting Passivhaus standards has significantly reduced carbon emissions and improved energy performance. However, HQM has achieved better results, but only in terms of reducing CO₂ emissions.

5. Conclusion

The quest for sustainability in term of energy efficiency and CO₂ emission, has put the construction industry under immense pressure from the government and the public to improve project delivery sustainability targets. Therefore, to overcome the reluctance of developers to embrace sustainability, it is imperative to reform the existing regulatory structure with the aim of simplification and effectiveness. Several key areas need to be considered when reformulating sustainability regulations and standards, such as the regulatory complexity, where this study confirms previous research findings – notably by Hummel & Rötzel (2019), Fischer & Guy (2009) and Decker (2018) – that the current regulatory framework is overly complex and characterised by significant overlap. This complexity poses challenges for developers, particularly those with limited resources, as it can hinder their ability to adopt sustainable practices. In addition, the difficulties in defining and distinguishing between different regulatory approaches, such as the roles and responsibilities of local authorities. This ambiguity can lead to confusion and uncertainty for both regulators and regulated businesses, especially when contextual factors such as the timing, context complexity and the nature of the regulated activities come into play to contribute to this challenge.

As noted from the mapping of sustainability regulations, the complexity of building regulations has reached a level where it may not be entirely understandable. Furthermore, in their current descriptive form, these regulations lack detailed guidance on how to achieve sustainability goals. The inclusion of a "comply-or-explain" clause has also had a significant impact on the UK's progress towards a sustainable and decarbonised housing sector. There is also clear evidence that embracing voluntary standards such as HQM and Passivhaus can lead to a lower environmental impact. Moreover, voluntary standards have proven to be more successful as they provide sufficient detail and explanation to achieve the desired goals by having a clear scope aligned with the actual needs of the sector. This reduces the gap between objectives and outcomes when compared to mandatory regulations. Nonetheless, these standards still fall outside the structure of mandatory regulations, which represent a missed opportunity to strike a balance between performance and prescriptive-based approaches to sustainability regulations.

6. Limitations and further development

The selection of case studies was primarily aimed at projects with similar

conditions such as location, typology and use. However, aspects such as the architectural layout, the material used or the construction method were not analysed or investigated in this study. Therefore, the authors suggest that future research addressing these variables is still needed.

We also, propose that the findings of this study can form the basis of a comprehensive decision support framework. This framework could be developed to help property developers navigate the complicated structure of sustainability regulations and their rapid change.

7. Acknowledgement and funding

The authors would like to thank the architectural firms and local authority planning departments who generously provided the necessary data and information for the case studies. This study was developed as part of a larger research project entitled RE-DWELL, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 956082.

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